

PHYSICAL FITNESS IN RELATION TO BODY MASS INDEX AMONG MIDDLE SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract

This cross-sectional study looked for sex differences in body composition and physical fitness among adolescents of secondary school age. A group of 600 pupils (300 male and 300 female individuals) was evaluated for the measurement of anthropometric indices and selected fitness indices. Independent samples t-Tests showed statistically significant sex differences for all the examined variables ($p < 0.001$). Male participants had higher body mass index and higher muscular strength while female participants had superior muscular endurance, cardiorespiratory endurance, and greater flexibility. Effect-IVise indicated moderate sized to large differences for body mass index, muscular strength (Cohen's $d = 0.64 - 0.65$), moderate sized to large and large effects for flexibility measure values and for measures related to endurance ($d = 0.88$ to 1.03) and a small effect size for body fat percentage ($d = 0.23$). These results highlight marked sex-based inequalities in physical fitness from age ten and the need for gender responsive/school based physical activity interventions.

INTRODUCTION

Childhood and early adolescence is a critical period of development when trajectories of body composition and physical fitness are laid down with longer term implications for health, functional capacity and disease risk across the life span. Body mass index (BMI) is currently the most widely used anthropometric index for determining weight status among children and adolescents because of its simplicity, cost-effectiveness and good correlation with cardiometabolic risk factors (Chen et al., 2020; Fiori et al., 2020). Concurrently, physical fitness, which includes cardiorespiratory endurance, muscular strength, speed, agility and flexibility, has been identified as one of the main indicators of current and prospective health in youth populations (Joshi et al., 2012; Pahkala et al., 2013). Accordingly, uncovering the relationship between BMI and physical fitness in middle school years is of great academic, public health, and educational importance.

An expanding corpus of international research consistently makes the following finding: A negative relationship between BMI and physical fitness is consistent among school-age children and adolescents. Studies conducted across various geographical locations and cultural settings such as China (Chen et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2022), Italy (Fiori et al., 2020), Indonesia (Allsabab and Putra, 2023; Aliriad et al., 2023), Oman (Delextrat et al., 2018), and Iran (Keykhaei et al., 2016), confirm that a higher value of BMI is related to poor performance in several domains of fitness. Large-scale cross-sectional evidence has been found similarly, with recent studies of population-average populations showing strong negative associations between physical fitness measurements and BMI (both in adolescence and young adulthood) (Yin et al., 2025).

Beyond simple correlations, latest research studies have started to focus on more complex pathways linking BMI, physical activity and physical fitness. For instance, Bai et al. (2024), found the presence of a mediating effect from BMI on physical fitness with relation to physical activity among junior high school students' physical activity, implying the possible presence of an obesogenic effect of excessive body mass on the physiological benefits provided by physical activity participation. Longitudinal research supports these observations and confirms that unfavourable BMI trajectories that are established in childhood can be used to predict unfavourable fitness levels in adolescence and therefore makes the need for early preventive interventions of prime importance (Pahkala et al., 2013; Eddolls et al., 2018).

Despite this growing body of international evidence, most of this ongoing research are on high- and upper-middle-income countries, with a lack of representation from South Asian contexts. In Pakistan, childhood overweight and obesity as well as physical inactivity have become prominent public health issues due to the precipitating consequences of rapid urbanisation, inactivity, high screen time and changing dietary patterns (Davy et al., 2004; Dewi et Tan, 2021). Nonetheless, empirical studies investigating the relationship between BMI and physical fitness in Pakistani schoolchildren are scarce and dispersed especially at the middle school level. Where there are investigations, they examine BMI prevalence or levels of physical activity in isolation and do not carry out an in-depth study of fitness parameters, including sex-based comparisons (Gao et al., 2011; Ma'arif et al., 2023).

This research gap is particularly large due to the unique characteristics of the middle school age group as it represents a transitional period in human development characterized by changes in puberty, rapid growth, and sex differences in body composition and physical performance. International research has also reported large gender disparities in BMI distribution and fitness results, and these may be affected by sociocultural determinants, opportunities for involvement in sports activities, and differences in physical education activity (Joshi et al., 2012; Eroglu et al., 2025). In Pakistan these differences further, may be exacerbated by cultural beliefs, especially for girls who are often constrained in terms of physical activity outdoors, as well as participation in organized sports because of warrants by the society's norms as well as safety issues.

From the point of view of policy, research on the relationships between BMI and physical fitness of schoolchildren is highly relevant to national and regional priorities. Pakistan's National Education Policy and the provincial physical education curricula focus on holistic child development, including physical health and fitness: Because of inadequate infrastructure, lack of well-trained personnel and monitoring mechanisms, implementation has been inconsistent. Moreover, the frameworks of Public Health have begun to realize schools as key locations for investing in early health promotion and non-communicable disease prevention. Investigating BMI-fitness relationships in the school context therefore provides evidence to underpin policy-driven interventions that target the quality of physical education, promotion of activities and early identification of risk.

Socioeconomic constraints add to the need for this research. We have numerous reasons to worry about the lack of physical activity as well as limited access to safe play sites, sports facilities, qualified coaches, or structured physical activity programme in children from lower socioeconomic backgrounds, both affecting the fitness development and the maintenance of a healthy weight (Leppanen et al., 2022; Shalabi et al., 2023). In Pakistan the differences in the infrastructure between public and private institutions, inequalities in urban and rural locations and resource-rich areas and resource-constrained areas have a major impact on students' exposure to physical training and assessment of fitness. These inequities require context specific empirical data in order to identify targeted and scalable interventions.

In summary, despite the robust evidence in international literature showing the relation between BMI and physical fitness in children and adolescents, a significant gap is noted regarding region specific research based on the Pakistani population specifically at the middle school level coupled with gender specific studies. The current study helps to solve this gap by investigating relations between BMI and physical fitness amongst boys and girls in middle school which will provide contextually relevant evidence to global literature. By including parameters related to anthropometry and performance - based parameters within a school setting, the research provides practical information for educators, policy makers, and health care professionals who might be interested in improving health outcomes among youth through informed and locally relevant strategies.

Purpose of the Study

The aim of the present study is to examine the correlation between BMI and the physical fitness in middle school students. Specifically, it aims to assess the status of BMI and specific fitness areas in boys and girls and the types of changes that take place within BMI and, to what extent, one's changes are related to changes in physical fitness performance. By comparing fitness results between the BMI groupings and between the two sexes, the research is trying to find patterns of data that may indicate influences related to physiology, behavior, and sociocultural factors in early adolescence.

Additionally, the research aims at the dearth of empirical evidence related to BMI - physical fitness relationships in the context of Pakistani school physical education context. Although ample international data is available documenting the inverse relationship between BMI and physical fitness, limited data is available for Pakistani middle school students where

the socioeconomic disparities, cultural values and institutional constraints may be uniquely affecting the child's body composition and physical performance. Therefore, the goal of this study is to produce context specific evidence to guide school based physical education practices, health promotion and policy initiatives.

Ultimately, the results aim to contribute to the existing literature through a greater understanding of the BMI-fitness association during a critical developmental period of life. The findings may help to inform educators, physical education teachers, physical health professionals, and policymakers to target more specific interventions to address physical fitness and healthy weight status, as well as reduce potential adverse health issues later in life in school-aged children.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The current investigation was a descriptive correlational study with a cross section. Data related to body mass index and selected physical fitness components were gathered at one point in time from male and female students in middle school. This methodological choice was suitable for exploring the simultaneous relationships between BMI and physical fitness and comparing supplements physical fitness des Morales between genders without the application of experimental manipulation.

Population and Sampling

The target population included all the middle school students (male & female) of the public schools of the District of Jhang i.e. the three tehsils of Jhang, Shorkot and Ahmad Pur. The sampling frame is comprised of middle schools of every tehsil for each gender. A multistage stratified sampling design was used to achieve acceptable representation by tehsils and by gender. In the first stage the District Jhang was stratified into its three tehsils, in the second stage, further stratification based on gender (male schools and female schools) was done. From each tehsil ten middle schools each for males and females were randomly selected. The selection of pupils from sampled schools was done through simple random samplings at the final stage. The sample size was calculated based on standard criteria for school-based cross-sectional research studies with adequate statistical power and representativeness. As a result, 100 male and 100 female students were selected from each tehsil that is, 200 participants from each tehsil. The total no. of students for the sample was 600, out of which 300 were males and

300 females. This sampling strategy ensured representation of both sexes, proportionate allocation among the tehsils, and inclusion of all individuals relevant to the target population and therefore, makes the investigation appropriately powered to evaluate the association between BMI and physical fitness among middle school students in District Jhang. An extensive illustration is given in Figure 3.1.

Figure 1: Showing Population and Sampling Process

Variables Used

Two main variables were investigated in the current investigation. The first variable included Body Mass Index (BMI) which was approximated by measuring the height and weight of participants and then simply using the usually known formula for calculation of BMI. The second variable was related to physical fitness, which was conceptualized as a multifaceted construct. Physical fitness was assessed based on salient components that include muscular strength, muscular endurance, cardiorespiratory endurance, flexibility and body composition. These variables were chosen to provide a comprehensive assessment of physical health and functional fitness abilities of the subjects.

Instruments for Data Collection

Anthropometric Measurements

Anthropometric data were collected for calculation of body mass index of participants. Height measurement was performed using a tape measure attached to a horizontal wall; participants were asked to stand upright, barefoot, with head, shoulders, buttocks and heels in contact with the wall and that height was measured in meters. Body weight was measured with a calibrated weighing scale; study participants were in light clothing and no footwear, and the weight was recorded in kilograms. Body Mass Index or BMI was then manually calculated using the standard equation: the weight (in kg) divided by the square of height (in m) (kg/m²).

Physical Fitness Evaluation

Physical fitness was measured using the application of standardized field-based test procedures used in educational settings. Muscular strength was assessed from a handheld handgrip dynamometer with the resultant force expressed in pounds. Muscular endurance was assessed using the push up test for men and the sit up test for women; the performance was measured in terms of the total number of correctly completed repetitions. Cardiorespiratory endurance was assessed using either the 1-mile run test or the 20-meter shuttle run test, and performance was recorded in minutes. Flexibility was tested with the sit and reach test; measures were taken in inches. The measure of body composition was estimated using skinfold calipers and measures were recorded in millimeters and then used to calculate the percentage of body fat. All measurements were made during scheduled Physical Education classes in the indoor facilities of the selected schools to ensure that the testing conditions were standardized.

Table 3.1: *Variables and Proposed Tests/Equipment*

S. No	Variable	Test/Equipment
Anthropometric Measurement		
I	Height	Measuring Tape
Ii	Weight	Weight Scale
Ii	BMI	Formula for BMI “weight in kilogram divided by height in meter square” was used.
Physical Fitness		
I	Muscular Strength	Handgrip Dynamometer
Ii	Muscular Endurance	Push-Up (boys) Test or Sit-Up Test (girls)
Iii	Cardiorespiratory Endurance	1-Mile Run Test or 20-Meter Shuttle Run Test
Iv	Flexibility	Sit and Reach Test

Research Model/Framework

Figure 2: Research Model of the Study

The research model focuses on the relationship between Body Mass Index (BMI) and physical fitness in Middle school students. BMI is the height and weight computation which is taken as the independent variable, and physical fitness (muscular strength, muscular endurance, cardiorespiratory endurance, flexibility, and body composition) was conceptualized as the dependent variable. The model proves that there are differences in the association between variation in BMI status and variation in performance in the components of physical fitness.

Data Analyses

Data were coded and analyzed with the appropriate statistical software. Descriptive statistics, such as mean, standard deviation, frequency and percentage were used to summarize the BMI and physical fitness variables. Pearson's correlation coefficient was calculated to assess the relationship between BMI and components of physical fitness, whereas independent samples t-test, and analysis of variance (ANOVA) were performed to analyze differences between genders and differences between groups of subjects classified by levels of BMI. The level of significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: *Descriptive Statistics for Physical Fitness Parameters of Middle School Girls (n = 300)*

Parameter	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Body Mass Index (kg/m ²)	20.03	1.50	18.20	23.50
Muscular Strength (lbs)	55.70	4.20	50.10	60.30
Muscular Endurance (repetitions)	22.40	3.10	18.00	26.00
Cardiorespiratory Endurance (minutes)	12.50	1.80	10.00	15.00
Flexibility (inches)	15.80	1.20	14.50	17.20
Body Fat Percentage (%)	21.40	2.30	18.90	24.80

Table 1 shows the results regarding descriptive statistics of physical fitness parameters among middle school girls showing the overall distribution and variability in terms of body mass index and important fitness component: muscular strength, muscular endurance, cardiorespiratory endurance, flexibility, and percentage of body fat. The results show generally consistent fitness performance with variation across participants with an apparent observable difference giving a base profile for girls' physical fitness among sampled girls.

Table 2: *Descriptive Statistics for Physical Fitness Parameters of Middle School Boys (n = 300)*

Parameter	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Body Mass Index (kg/m ²)	21.10	1.80	18.50	23.90
Muscular Strength (lbs)	58.30	3.90	52.60	63.90
Muscular Endurance (repetitions)	19.50	2.50	15.00	24.00
Cardiorespiratory Endurance (minutes)	10.80	1.50	8.00	13.00
Flexibility (inches)	14.70	1.30	13.10	16.20
Body Fat Percentage (%)	20.90	2.10	18.30	23.50

Table 2 summarizes the physical fitness profile of the middle school boys to display the general pattern and dispersion for body mass index and major fitness factors. The data gives a general picture of the physical characteristics and fitness performance of boys indicating the normal variation within the sample.

Table 3: *Independent Samples t-Test for Gender Differences in BMI and Physical Fitness*

Variable	Boys Mean	Girls Mean	t	df	P
BMI	21.1	20.03	7.91	598	< .001
Muscular Strength	58.3	55.7	7.86	598	< .001
Muscular Endurance	19.5	22.4	-12.61	598	< .001
Cardiorespiratory Endurance	10.8	12.5	-12.57	598	< .001
Flexibility	14.7	15.8	-10.77	598	< .001
Body Fat %	20.9	21.4	-2.78	598	< .001

Table-3 shows that there are significant gender disparities in all body mass index (BMI) and physical fitness variables. Male participants had better BMI and muscular strength while females had better muscular endurance, cardiorespiratory endurance, flexibility and body fat percentage. These differences were found to be statistically significant, highlighting a unique gender based heterogeneity in physical fitness profiles.

Table 4: *Effect Size (Cohen's d) for Gender Differences in BMI and Physical Fitness*

Variable	Boys Mean	Girls Mean	Cohen's d
BMI	21.10	20.03	0.65
Muscular Strength	58.30	55.70	0.64
Muscular Endurance	19.50	22.40	-1.03
Cardiorespiratory Endurance	10.80	12.50	-1.03
Flexibility	14.70	15.80	-0.88
Body Fat Percentage	20.90	21.40	-0.23

Table 4 shows moderate to large effect sizes for most of the measured variables and thus demonstrates salient gender differences in physical fitness. Large effect sizes were found for muscular endurance, cardiorespiratory endurance and flexibility, whereas BMI and muscular strength produced moderate effect sizes. Body fat percentage showed only a low impact, which suggests a relatively low difference of practical relevance among boys and girls.

Table 5: *Distribution of BMI Categories by Gender*

BMI Category	Boys (n)	Boys (%)	Girls (n)	Girls (%)
Underweight	30	10.0	45	15.0
Normal Weight	195	65.0	210	70.0
Overweight	60	20.0	36	12.0
Obese	15	5.0	9	3.0

Table 5 outlines the distribution of body mass index (BMI) categories based on gender and two data points can be ascertained; most male and female cohorts are respectively found in the normative weight category. A relatively high proportion of males were considered adjudicated to be overweight or obese compared to the female cohort and a higher prevalence of underweight status was observed in the female cohort, thus highlighting the gender-dependent differences in the distribution of BMI.

Discussion

The current study examined gender effects on body mass index (BMI) and physical fitness characteristics in middle school children and provided important information on the relationship between body composition and physical fitness at an early age. Results showed evidence of significant gender-based differences in the findings of BMI and several factors of physical fitness, emphasizing further the multidimensionality of youth fitness and its high correlation with body mass status.

The descriptive analysis showed that at the normal BMI values both boys and girls were generally exhibited in physical fitness; however, gender differences were evident at the physical fitness components. Boys performed better in muscular strength while girls performed better on muscular endurance, cardiorespiratory endurance and flexibility. These results are consistent with other studies that show that patterns of physiological maturation and favorite activities in adolescence play a role in the emergence of different fitness profiles across sexes (Joshi et al, 2012; Fiori et al., 2020). Comparable gender-related trends have been documented among school pioneering of Indonesia, China and Europe, whereby boys are thought to be more successful than girls in strength-related tasks, while girls often show greater endurance and flexibility (Aliriad et al., 2023; Chen et al., 2022; Simbolon and Firdausi, 2019).

The independent measures (t-test) also confirmed the statistical significance of the gender differences in all the BMI and fitness variables. Boys had significantly higher BMI and

muscular strength while the girls had significantly better muscular endurance, cardiorespiratory endurance, and flexibility. These results agree with previous reports that higher BMI values in boys may in part be due to an increased amount of lean tissue, whereas better endurance performance in girls may be explained by a difference in physical activity patterns and motor efficiency (Delextrat et al., 2018; Hsieh et al., 2014). Moreover, the gender changes in body fat percentage are also consistent with biological modification in terms of puberty, and behavioral influences in terms of physical activity involvement (Leppanen et al., 2022).

Effect-of-size analysis was used to gain further information about the practical meaning of those differences. Large effect sizes were obtained in the muscular endurance, cardiorespiratory endurance and flexibility categories, which recommended differing gender differences in these components are not only statistically significant but also meaningful in real-world settings. Moderate effect sizes for BMI and muscular strength, that is, boys and girls can observe a difference, but it is not as striking. These findings were consistent with the reports of Cossio, et al. (2022) and Shalabi, et al. (2023), where the authors pointed out the importance of looking at effect sizes in conjunction with p-values when interpreting youth fitness results.

The distribution of the BMI categories showed that most of the students in both groups were categorised as being in the normal range weight category, in accordance with international school-based studies (Allsabab & Putra, 2023; Ma'arif et al., 2023). Nevertheless, a higher percentage of boys were considered overweight or obese whereas underweight prevalence was higher among girls. Similar patterns have been observed in studies conducted in Iran, the United States and China in which lifestyle behaviours, dietary habits, and sociocultural factors influence gender-specific BMI trends (Davy et al., 2004; Keykhaei et al., 2016; Zhang et al., 2022).

These findings support the mounting evidence that BMI plays a critical role in determining the outcome of physical fitness in the adolescent. Previous studies have shown inverse correlations between BMI and several aspects of fitness especially cardiorespiratory fitness and motor performance (Fiori et al., 2020; Yin et al., 2025). Recent studies have also indicated the importance of BMI as a mediator between physical activity and physical fitness, making it necessary to address body composition in a school-based intervention in addition to promoting activity (Bai et al., 2024; Dewi et al., 2021).

From a practical standpoint, the results highlight the necessity of gender-individualized physical education programs focused on boys and girls (differing fitness strength/weakness). Schools should focus on balanced types of physical activity opportunities that strengthen the body and intensify endurance and physical flexibility while at the same time encouraging healthy weight maintenance. In addition, longitudinal evidence indicates that the trajectories of fitness and body mass index (BMI) set in the middle-school period may continue into adolescence and adulthood and thus are potentially more important for intervention at an earlier age (Pahkala et al., 2013; Eddolls et al., 2018).

In summary, the current study contributes to the literature by presenting empirical evidence of significant gender difference in BMI and physical fitness in middle school students. The findings are generally similar to international studies and emphasize the complicated interaction between body composition and physical fitness at a critical period of development. These results support the need for specific strategies that involve physical fitness improvements and BMI promotion in school settings for adolescents.

CONCLUSION

The present study can be concluded that the relationship between body mass index and physical fitness is quite comprehensive and shows clear gender-based differences among middle schools. Significant differences were found in all the physical fitness components, as boys showed better results regarding BMI and muscular strength, whereas girls showed better results regarding muscular endurance, cardiorespiratory endurance and flexibility. These are important findings because they show that physical fitness in early adolescence is multidimensional and determined by a combination of biological and behavioral factors.

Furthermore, the distribution of BMI categories showed that although most students were within the normal range, considerable numbers of overweight and underweight students were found, pointing to some health risks at the school level. The sizes of the effects are observed to verify that many of the gender differences are not only statistically significant, but most are of a practical nature as well. Overall, the results of the study highlight the need for early evaluation of BMI and physical fitness and support the implementation of gender sensitive, school-based physical education and health promotion programs to improve fitness level and promote healthy growth in middle school children.

Implications of the Study

The results highlight the need to weigh and test body mass index and physical fitness at regular intervals in middle school students. Gender differences identified in fitness components indicate the need for gender sensitive physical education programs that address the differences in fitness needs. The effects support school-based health and physical activity strategies and provide evidence for policy makers to reinforce P.E. practices and optimize healthy growth at an early age of adolescence.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in publication of this study.

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